

Newsletter 4 / 2021

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Contents

Save the date	2
Online course on Code Coupling with OASIS3-MCT from 29 April to 12 May, 2021	2
Spread the word	2
Beta testers wanted!	2
Talk on the EC's DestinE programme	2
Events that ESIWACE will participate in or has participated in	2
News & updates	3
ESiWACE contributions to the vEGU 2021 General Assembly	3
Joint IS-ENES3/ESiWACE2 Virtual Workshop on New Opportunities for ML and AI in Weather and Climate Modelling	4
Snapshots	5
Recent ESIWACE2-related Publications	7
News from the neighbors	7

Save the date

Online course on Code Coupling with OASIS3-MCT from 29 April to 12 May, 2021

Registration open until Wednesday, 14 April, 2021

The next Small Private Online Course on OASIS3-MCT, funded by ESIWACE2, will take place from Thursday 29 April, 2021 to Wednesday 12 May, 2021. The whole course should require about 20 hours of work to spend over the two weeks. OASIS3-MCT is a coupling library that can be used to exchange information between different codes modelling the different components of the Earth System, e.g. the ocean or the atmosphere. In this training, mixing theory, videos, quizzes and hands-on, you will learn how to use OASIS3-MCT. Your goal will be to instrument two toy models in order to set up a real coupled model exchanging coupling fields.

For more information and registration, please see the [official training page](#).

Spread the word

Beta testers wanted!

New python and C interfaces are now available for coupling python and C components through the OASIS3-MCT coupler. This development was funded by the IS-ENES3 EU project. We are looking for beta testers! If you are interested, please contact us at sophie.valcke@cerfacs.fr.

Talk on the EC's DestinE programme

Peter Bauer and Nils Wedi from ECMWF outline in a talk how the European Commission's Destination Earth (DestinE) programme transforms environmental policy making with digital twins as a step-change for Earth-system modelling and data assimilation. More information can be found [here](#), the slides and recordings of the talk are available [here](#).

Events that ESIWACE will participate in or has participated in

- [PASC21](#), Geneva, Switzerland / online, 5-8 July, 2021
- [ISC 2021 High Performance Digital](#), online, 24 June - July 2, 2021
- [Teratec Forum 2021](#), online, 22-24 June, 2021

- [EGU General Assembly vEGU: Gather Online](#), online, 19-30 April, 2021
- [Joint IS-ENES3/ESiWACE2 virtual workshop on New Opportunities for Machine Learning & Artificial Intelligence in weather and climate modelling](#), online, 16-18 March, 2021

News & updates

ESiWACE contributions to the vEGU 2021 General Assembly

Session on “High resolution modelling of weather and climate” convened by Peter Dueben, Daniel Klocke and Florian Ziemen. The session is planned for [Thu 29 April 09:00-11:45 CEST](#)

<https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU21/session/40829>

- Presentation on **“The DYAMOND Winter data collection”** by Julia Duras, Florian Ziemen and Daniel Klocke
Thursday, 29 Apr, 09:16-9:18 CEST
- Presentation on **“GPU acceleration of the FESOM-2 ocean and sea-ice model”** by Gijs van den Oord, Alessio Sclocco, Georges-Emmanuel Moulard, David Guibert, Dmitry Sidorenko, Nikolay Koldunov, Ben van Werkhoven, Erwan Raffin, and Natalja Rakowski
Thursday, 29 Apr, 09:34-9:36 CEST
- Presentation on **DYAMOND-II simulations with IFS-FESOM2** by Thomas Rackow, Nils Wedi, Kristian Mogensen, Peter Dueben, Helge F. Goessling, Jan Hegewald, Christian Kühnlein, Lorenzo Zampieri, and Thomas Jung
Thursday, 29 Apr, 09:36–09:38 CEST
- Presentation on **Operational Single-Precision Earth-System Modelling at ECMWF** by Sam Kristian Mogensen, Peter Dueben, Nils Wedi, and Michail Diamantakis
Thursday, 29 Apr, 09:38–09:40 CEST
- Presentation on **“OBLIMAP parallelization and optimization toward high resolution climate model - ice sheet model coupler”** by Erwan Raffin, David Guibert and Thomas Reerink
Thursday, 29 Apr, 09:40-9:42 CEST

Session on “Machine learning for Earth System modelling” convened by Julien Brajard, Peter Dueben, Redouane Lguensat, Francine Schevenhoven, Maike Sonnewald. The session is planned for **Fri, 30 April, 11:00-17:00 CEST** <https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU21/session/40110>

- Presentation on **Machine-Learned Preconditioners for Linear Solvers in Geophysical Fluid Flows** by Jan Ackmann, Peter Dueben, Tim Palmer and Piotr Smolarkiewicz
Friday, 30 Apr, 11:21-11:23 CEST
- Presentation on **Machine Learning Emulation of 3D Cloud Radiative Effects** by David Meyer, Robin J. Hogan, Peter D. Dueben, and Shannon L. Mason
Friday, 30 Apr, 13:46–13:48 CEST
- Presentation on **Machine learning emulation of gravity wave drag in numerical weather forecasting** by Matthew Chantry, Sam Hatfield, Peter Dueben, Inna Polichtchouk and Tim Palmer
Friday 30 Apr, 13:54-13:56 CEST

Joint IS-ENES3/ESIWACE2 Virtual Workshop on New Opportunities for ML and AI in Weather and Climate Modelling

This workshop was a joint collaboration with IS-ENES3 with the aim of bringing together climate scientists and experts from academia and industry to share knowledge and experience and to identify new opportunities in the areas of machine learning, artificial intelligence and big data techniques for weather and climate modelling.

The workshop was organised around three three-and-a-half hour sessions, each commencing at 3pm CET:

- Views from Domain Science (Day 1)
- ML/AI Software Technologies (Day 2)
- High performance, Infrastructure and Big data Challenges (Day 3)

Of the total of 21 speakers, 15 were from academic institutions and weather and climate centres around the world. Six were from industry, representing both software and hardware technology developers as well as service providers. Each session day was structured with seven talks and a panel session. The workshop was very well attended with a total of 206 unique participants taking part in the three sessions (out of a total of 287 registrations). We had 173 participants attending on day 1, 136 participants on day 2 and 97 participants on day 3. They had a range of backgrounds from across academia, weather and climate centres and industry around the world. More information and presentation slides are available on the [event page](#).

Snapshots

Atos Bull

Atos Bull started working on several newly granted HPC services: AGRIF, FESOM2 and RTE+RRTMGP C++ in collaboration with NLeSC.

BSC

BSC participated in the Virtual EC-Earth meeting (8 to 11 February) where discussions on the EC-Earth4 model took place. BSC is working with other partners on different aspects of the model to deliver an updated and improved model version. Finally, BSC will present a scalability analysis of the main EC-Earth4 components (OpenIFS 43R3 i NEMO4) at the next EGU General Assembly.

CERFACS

CERFACS is working on completing the Small Private Online Course (SPOC) on OASIS3-MCT with additional hands-on to ease the usage of the coupler. The next SPOC session will take place from Thursday 29 April, 2021 to Wednesday 12 May, 2021. In the past few months, CERFACS has also been actively working on improving OASIS3-MCT functionalities. Some of them are funded through IS-ENES3, like the new python interface and the analysis of different interpolation libraries, and some of them are realised thanks to ESiWACE2, like the development of new API routines to set up MPI intercomm and intracomm communicators between two coupled components and the update of the compiling environment.

CMCC

CMCC is working on an intermediate release of the ESDM extensions for post-processing, analytics and visualization (PAV). In particular, the ESDM PAV runtime is being further improved to target larger-scale experiments, while the Python library is being extended to provide graphical monitoring of PAV experiment execution. Additionally, the new Ophidia import/export operators integrating the ESDM library have been further improved. CMCC has contributed to deliverable D4.1 “Advanced software stack for Earth system data” describing these Ophidia extension activities. Moreover, CMCC has been involved in the organisation of the joint IS-ENES3/ESiWACE2 Virtual Workshop on New Opportunities for ML and AI in Weather and Climate Modelling, held on March 16-18, 2021.

DKRZ

DKRZ and MPI-M are currently working on running coupled ICON model simulations with spatial resolutions of 10km, 5km, and 2.5km. In the last three months, DYAMOND Winter data sets have been arriving at DKRZ. As of now, data of six models with one to three runs per model have been transferred. DKRZ is currently checking these data sets for completeness and consistency before they will be published for scientific analysis. Find details on the DYAMOND intercomparison at <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/dyiamond/>. In addition, DKRZ has worked on the extension of the Paraview CDI reader to support additional models to unify the visualisation workflow and to improve support for missing value treatment, as well as towards an upgrade of the reader within the official version of ParaView.

Jointly with ESIWACE2 and IS-ENES3 partners, DKRZ has also been involved in organising and hosting the Joint IS-ENES3/ESIWACE2 Virtual Workshop on New Opportunities for ML and AI in Weather and Climate Modelling.

ECMWF

First simulations with single precision in IFS, NEMO and the wave model have been performed for extended-range periods. Skill scores are promising, but not yet neutral compared with double precision. Fully single precision seasonal experiments are now undergoing testing.

Further work on the non-hydrostatic spectral IFS is ongoing with the hope to run a non-hydrostatic (uncoupled) IFS run with 2.5 km grid-spacing for DYAMOND.

ETH Zürich / CSCS

CSCS is slowly gearing up for the “C++ for HPC” course. Because of the pandemic we will have to wait for some months before we can know for sure whether it will be a physical or virtual course (or a combination). More information to follow.

Met Office

It is a time of fast development and big changes in LFRic. Final preparations for the new LFRic model release are underway. The release will also serve as a fixed point for development during the time of transition to the upcoming PSyclone release. Changes in the entire LFRic code base are required to make use of the new PSyclone features, such as i-first looping for the Physics kernels, support for fields of different primitive types and preliminary support for mixed precision. Evaluation of performance benefits of these new features in LFRic is soon to follow.

UKRI/STFC

Work continues on generating a performant GPU version of NEMO and the translation from PSyclone’s internal representation (PSyIR) to Dawn’s internal representation (SIR). Collaboration continues with CMCC (working in the IMMERSE project) on NEMO loop transformations and they now have a working transformation. Funding has been awarded to STFC to look at generating Met Office adjoint kernels from their tangent linear versions (derived from the LFRic dynamical core) to support the new Next Generation Modelling System (NGMS) Met Office Data Assimilation (DA) system.

UniMan

UniMan led the organisation of the “Virtual Workshop on New Opportunities in ML/AI for Weather and Climate” held on the 16-18 March 2021 and also acted as the general chair for the meeting.

University of Reading

We were completing Deliverable 4.1 (Advanced software stack for Earth system data). Also, the documentation of ESDM was improved, the support for ESDM was ported to the current version of NetCDF, additional tools were tested and adjusted where necessary, such as CDO and ParaView.

Recent ESIWACE2-related Publications

Benacchio T., Bonaventura L., Altenbernd M., et al.: Resilience and fault tolerance in high-performance computing for numerical weather and climate prediction. The International Journal of High Performance Computing Applications. February 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094342021990433>, 2021.

Christoudias, T., Kirfel, T., Kerkweg, A., Taraborrelli, D., Moulard, G.-E., Raffin, E., Azizi, V., van den Oord, G., and van Werkhoven, B.: GPU Optimizations for Atmospheric Chemical Kinetics. In The International Conference on High Performance Computing in Asia-Pacific Region (HPC Asia 2021). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 136–138. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3432261.3439863>, 2021.

Judt, F., Klocke, D., Rios-Berrios, R. et. al.: Tropical Cyclones in Global Storm-Resolving Models, JMSJ, II, 2021-029, <https://doi.org/10.2151/jmsj.2021-029>, 2021

Raffin, E., Guibert, D., and Reerink, T.: OBLIMAP parallelization and optimization toward high resolution climate model - ice sheet model coupler, EGU General Assembly 2021, online, 19–30 Apr 2021, EGU21-9880, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu21-9880>, 2021.

van den Oord, G., Sclocco, A., Moulard, G.-E., Guibert, D., Sidorenko, D., Koldunov, N., van Werkhoven, B., Raffin, E., and Rakowski, N.: GPU acceleration of the FESOM-2 ocean and sea-ice model, EGU General Assembly 2021, online, 19–30 Apr 2021, EGU21-11551, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu21-11551>, 2021.

News from the neighbors

IS-ENES3 Newsletter March 2021 : Check their new compute-to-data services, their Summer School on climate data use for impact assessments, upcoming workshops, new publications and software releases !

<https://mailchi.mp/dd18c5fe7bc7/is-enes3-newsletter-march-2021?e=669a346a59>

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